

Machine Learning Analysis Of Self-Consistent Magnetic Flux Ropes Realized In M-Dwarf Dynamo Simulations

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Abstract

The dynamical origins of the intense magnetic activity exhibited by most M-dwarf stars must be tied to their internal convective dynamos, and yet there remain many unanswered questions concerning its details. Despite the central role magnetic flux ropes are thought to play in the formation of solar and stellar starspots, global MHD simulations of stellar interiors have historically struggled to self-consistently capture their dynamics. By their nature, these structures tend to be short-lived or wholly absent in all but the most turbulent high-resolution simulations – environments which make their hand-identification and study prohibitively time-consuming. We present here a novel machine-learning pipeline for the autonomous identification and analysis of self-consistent, rising flux ropes found in our global 3D MHD simulations of M-dwarf convective interiors. We report on the details of the models developed, as well as early results from the project and its prospects moving forward.

1 Introduction

Despite their small sizes, cool temperatures, and dim luminosities, M-dwarf stars are well known for the vigorous magnetism many of them display. Unlike more massive stars, of which only 5-10% demonstrate chromospheric markers for magnetic activity, nearly all fully convective (FC) late M-dwarfs appear to be highly magnetically active (e.g. West et al. 2008; 2015). On such stars, flares are exceedingly common events (Kowalski et al., 2009). Some M-dwarfs appear to have surfaces nearly carpeted by magnetic fields at strengths similar to sunspots ($\sim 10^3$ G), and give off flares that may be a thousand times more energetic than those of the Sun (e.g. Kowalski et al. 2010; Silverberg et al. 2016; Davenport 2016). The magnetic fields responsible for this activity at the surface of a star must inevitably be tied to that star’s internal dynamo.

Although helio and asteroseismology can reveal some features of the flows occurring in stellar interiors, studies of their dynamo action are almost wholly the domain of theory and simulation. The intense separation of scales present in stellar convection zones (CZs), from global flow structures such as the differential rotation (DR) and meridional circulations (MC), to granulation occurring at 1 Mm, necessitates that computational approaches adopt various abstractions. Models which capture the stellar surface and atmosphere (e.g. Martínez-Sykora et al. 2012; Rempel 2012; Carlsson et al. 2016) have yielded great insights into the dynamics of granules, sunspots, and other surface structures, at the cost of very high resolution and computationally intensive physics. As a result, such models cannot reasonably be extended to encompass the entire star, and the shape and amplitude of magnetic flux emergence is typically prescribed at their lower boundaries.

By contrast, global simulations generally cannot hope to resolve the fine scales and supersonic speeds of flows at the stellar surface, and must exclude this region from their com-

putational domains. Models following this approach have greatly increased our understanding of the dynamics of flows and magnetic fields in the highly turbulent and nonlinear environment of a stellar CZ. Brown et al. (2010; 2011) were the first to show that large-scale organization of field and regular cycling was possible in the bulk of the CZ of a sun-like star, without the need for appealing to a tachocline of shear. In recent years, many features of the global solar dynamo have been recovered in different simulations, including equatorward migration of field and grand minima (Augustson et al., 2015), torsional oscillations (Guerrero et al., 2016), and hemispheric asymmetry (Matilsky & Toomre, 2020). Additionally, much work has been done unravelling the parameter regimes of these dynamo systems, which can be extremely sensitive (e.g. Nelson et al. 2013; Strugarek et al. 2018). The dynamo action of M-dwarf stars is largely unexplored by comparison, with work by Browning (2008) and later Yadav et al. (2015) demonstrating extremely strong magnetic fields built in the interiors of FC M-dwarfs. More recently, Bice & Toomre (2020) and Brown et al. (2020) have identified a preponderance of single-hemisphere dynamo modes operating in the stars’ deep CZs.

For all its successes, work on global dynamo simulations has struggled to self-consistently capture the formation and rise of the magnetic flux ropes which would become starspots. To date, only the work of Nelson et al. (2011; 2014), which employed a Dynamic Smagorinsky turbulence model to achieve much lower effective diffusivities, has indicated the presence of buoyantly rising superequipartition flux structures which maintain connectivity to the toroidal wreath of field at the heart of the dynamo. Other examinations of flux emergence from convective dynamo simulations do not maintain connectivity (Fan & Fang, 2014) or rely on injecting inviscid flux ropes that cannot back-react on the flows (e.g. Weber & Browning 2016).

The dearth of self-consistent rising flux ropes can be attributed to two main obstacles. First, their superequiparti-

Figure 1: (Left) Instantaneous radial velocity, v_r , and radial and azimuthal magnetic fields, B_r and B_ϕ , in Mollweide projection near the outer boundary of the domain and near mid-CZ of case D2ta from Bice & Toomre (2020). (Right) Longitude- and time-averaged differential rotation, $\langle \Omega \rangle = \langle v_\phi / r \sin \theta \rangle$, meridional circulation, $\langle \Psi \rangle$, and radial and azimuthal magnetic fields, B_r and B_ϕ .

tion field amplitudes and compact structures lead to rapid diffusion and dissolution in all but the most turbulent simulations. Second, identifying and tracking such structures in a resistive environment is extremely difficult and does not readily accommodate automation, mandating a great deal of time and energy investment from researchers with no guarantee of finding anything worthwhile. We introduce here a new dynamo simulation with self-consistently rising, well-connected flux ropes in an M2 star, as well as a set of machine-learning tools designed to identify and track such structures without reliance upon human guidance.

2 Convective Dynamo Simulation

For the simulation presented here, we employ the open-source 3D MHD code Rayleigh (Featherstone & Hindman, 2016) to evolve the anelastic compressible equations in rotating spherical shells. Rayleigh is a pseudospectral code, employing both a physical grid and a basis of spherical harmonics and Chebyshev polynomials. The anelastic equations are a fully nonlinear form of the fluid equations from which sound waves have been filtered out. This provides an appropriate framework for exploring subsonic convection within stellar interiors, where fast-moving p-modes would otherwise throttle the maximum timestep. The thermodynamic variables are linearized against a one-dimensional, time independent background state involving density, pressure, temperature, and entropy ($\bar{\rho}$, \bar{P} , \bar{T} , and \bar{S} , respectively), with deviations from the background written without overbars. As with all simulations of this type, the viscosity ν , conductivity κ , and resistivity η are inflated by many orders of magnitude as a parameterization of the turbulent mixing occurring at sub-grid scales. The detailed forms of the anelastic equations involving the velocity vector \mathbf{v} and the magnetic

field vector \mathbf{B} solved in Rayleigh are as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Momentum : } \bar{\rho} \left(\frac{D\mathbf{v}}{Dt} + 2\Omega_0 \hat{z} \times \mathbf{v} \right) = \\ - \bar{\rho} \nabla \frac{P}{\bar{\rho}} + \frac{\bar{\rho} g}{c_p} S + \nabla \cdot \mathcal{D} + \frac{1}{4\pi} (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Energy : } \bar{\rho} \bar{T} \frac{DS}{Dt} = \nabla \cdot [\kappa \bar{\rho} \bar{T} \nabla S] + \\ Q + \Phi + \frac{\eta}{4\pi} [\nabla \times \mathbf{B}]^2, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Induction : } \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} - \eta \nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \quad (3)$$

Here, Q is the volumetric heating function, \mathcal{D} is the viscous stress tensor, and Φ represents the viscous heating, which are defined as

$$\mathcal{D}_{ij} = 2\bar{\rho}\nu [e_{ij} - \frac{1}{3}(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v})\delta_{ij}]. \quad (4)$$

$$\Phi = 2\bar{\rho}\nu [e_{ij}e_{ij} - \frac{1}{3}(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v})^2], \quad (5)$$

with e_{ij} as the strain rate tensor. Additionally, both the mass flux and magnetic field are divergenceless: $\nabla \cdot (\bar{\rho}\mathbf{v}) = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$. Closure is achieved with a linearized equation of state,

$$\frac{P}{\bar{P}} = \frac{\rho}{\bar{\rho}} + \frac{T}{\bar{T}}. \quad (6)$$

The model highlighted in this work first appeared as case D2ta in Bice & Toomre (2020), and select visualizations from that work depicting its flow and magnetic fields are shown

Figure 2: (a) Magnetic field lines of the dynamo simulation at one instant, projected into the XZ-plane. Red lines have met a threshold score for "loopiness" defined by the classification neural network. (b) An example segmentation of a "loopy" magnetic field line. The red segment is a candidate magnetic loop, and the blue is discarded. (c) The volume of the loop structure is threaded by many nearby magnetic field lines. (d) Maximal radius of a random subset of loop candidates as a function of time. Loop candidates which undergo rapid rise through the CZ are highlighted in red, and less mobile loops have reduced opacity.

in Figure 1. To summarize the detailed description of its parameters and flows therein, case D2ta is a model of an M2 ($0.4M_{\odot}$) star whose domain includes 5 density scale-heights of the CZ, and extends $0.1R_*$ into the underlying radiative zone (RZ). The model is moderately turbulent, with a mid-depth fluctuating Reynolds number of $Re' = 96.1$. It rotates at twice the solar rate, leading to a solar-like differential rotation profile. A decrease of the diffusivities in the RZ leads to formation of a tachocline of shear there, though much of the differential rotation both there and in the CZ is suppressed by the Lorenz force. The magnetic Prandtl number $P_{rm} = \nu/\eta$, which sets the relative scales of viscous and resistive dissipation, is unity. In case D2ta, extremely strong axisymmetric toroidal fields on the order of 30 kG, with non-axisymmetric peaks exceeding 50 kG, develop in a wreath at the equator, and extend symmetrically to higher latitudes in the tachocline.

After maintaining its magnetic fields in this steady configuration for decades of simulation time, case D2ta was shaken up by the buoyant rise of superequipartition magnetic fields from the tachocline in its southern hemisphere. Interactions between this rising structure and a longitudinally enhanced nest of vigorous convection destabilized the entire reservoir of field there, which was dragged into the CZ where it too began to buoyantly rise. In total, this event led to the rise of $\sim 10^{37}$ erg of magnetic energy over a period of roughly 3 years. Due to the magnetic boundary conditions imposed on the model, this flux is not able to emerge, but instead resistively decays near the top of the domain. Inspection of the magnetic field lines during this interval has yielded an abun-

dance of rising magnetic loops, despite the fact that case D2ta is not, in general, well suited to produce them.

3 A Pipeline for Magnetic Loops

Taking the opportunity presented by our large catalogue of hand-identified magnetic loops, we have developed an automated routine by which data from global 3D spherical MHD simulations can be processed, systematically identifying and tracking the evolution of nearly all loop structures generated within the domain. In principle, the pipeline should also be applicable to data from simulation codes other than Rayleigh, provided they operate with spherical grids, and to stellar types other than M2, although re-training of the neural networks may be necessary to achieve the same level of accuracy in other domain geometries.

The process begins with snapshots of the full \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{B} fields, as well as the entropy S , at each instant to be considered. In order to track the loops between snapshots, it is important that the temporal spacing of the snapshots is not significantly longer than the shortest large-scale dynamical timescale in the CZ, in our case, the rotation period. In each snapshot, thousands of magnetic field lines are integrated from randomly seeded origin points. The distribution function for the origin points is uniform in space, ensuring that no regions of the volume are ignored, and that all magnetic structures are threaded by at least one such field line. All field lines are integrated to a fixed length of $s = 2R_*$ in 399 steps. At each position along each line, 11 parameters are recorded. These are the 3 spherical coordinates,

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the classifier network. Grey boxes represent the shape of the data at each stage. Blue boxes encode the width of the window for the convolutions and subsequent pooling represented by the red wedges. Arrows represent linear operations.

$\Delta\phi = \phi - \phi_0$, θ , and r , the cylindrical radius and height, $r_{cyl} = r \sin\theta$ and $z = |r \cos\theta|$, the curvature, signed by its radial component, $\kappa = \left\| \frac{d^2 \mathbf{r}}{ds^2} \right\| \left\| \frac{d^2 r/ds^2}{|d^2 r/ds^2|} \right\|$, the radial velocity v_r , the radial and horizontal magnetic field amplitudes, $|B_r|$ and $B_h = (B_\theta^2 + B_\phi^2)^{1/2}$, the log of the ratio of kinetic to magnetic energy, $\beta = \log(2\pi\rho v^2/B^2)$, and the fluctuation of entropy relative to a local mean $S' = S - \int_V S dV/V$ where V is a spherical wedge roughly $0.05R_*$ on a side.

These field lines are then fed into a binary classification neural network further described in §4, which attributes a score to each line based on the likelihood they contain at least one rising loop. Field lines not meeting a user-specified threshold for "loopiness" are then discarded. An example of this selection process is shown in Figure 2(a), with blue lines rejected and red continuing to the next stage in the routine. Selection by the classifier network is not a critical step to the overall functioning of the pipeline, however the relative simplicity of its architecture in comparison to that of the following network means that any culling of the data set here yields significant reductions in the overall computational expense.

Field lines selected by the classification network are then passed into another neural network designed for segmentation, again further described in §4. The output of the segmentation network indicates which parts, if any, of the field line appear to be rising loops. An example segmentation is shown in Figure 2(b), with the red section being flagged as a candidate loop. For each candidate loop, more field lines are densely seeded near the origin of the loop and integrated until they have the same length. Lines which remain sufficiently close to the loop candidate at some threshold fraction of points are deemed to belong to the same structure, and all others are discarded. The structures around each loop candidate in a particular snapshot are compared, and those with sufficient overlap are merged. An example structure formed this way is shown in Figure 2(c). The centroids of these merged structures are then used to estimate the location of the true core for each loop candidate, and their extents used to estimate the radius of each loop at each position along its length, thus defining a volume and further culling the data set.

The final stage of the pipeline concerns the tracking of loop candidates from one snapshot to the next. For each pair

of adjacent snapshots, loop candidates at the latter time are compared to earlier-time loops which have been advected by only the mean zonal flow $\mathbf{r}'_s = \mathbf{r}_s + \Delta t \langle v_\phi(\mathbf{r}_s) \rangle_\phi$. Matches are recorded for all loop candidate pairs which are sufficiently close, which often leads to multiplicity in potential matches. To ease computational burdens, each loop's furthest matches are culled until its match multiplicity is beneath a user-defined maximum. Once a list of matches in the next snapshot has been defined for each loop candidate, data for the full period of interest are aggregated and multi-timestep evolution trees are constructed. An example series tracking the maximum radial coordinate of loops over time is shown in Figure 2(d). At this point, the function of the pipeline is complete, and analysis of its data products is left to the user.

4 Machine Learning Models

The binary classification network developed for this project is adapted from the popular "AlexNet" model (Krizhevsky et al., 2017), which has seen great success in a variety of image classification problems. For our purposes, field lines are considered to be images with dimensions of 400px x 1px and 11 "color" channels containing the normalized quantities presented in Section 3. A schematic representation of the classification network is presented in Figure 3. It features two convolution layers, each followed by max pooling and linear rectification, followed three fully-connected linear layers, each followed by linear rectification, which reduce the system to an array with two values: measures of the likelihood that the input image belongs to each of two exclusive classes.

To train the classification network, we first assigned classifications by eye to 1900 field lines, based on whether or not they were judged to have loop-like features. While this undoubtedly introduces strong biases into the training set, we reiterate that the classification network is only used to quickly cull those field lines which clearly *do not* contain a loop. Of those 1900 lines, 402 were judged to be potentially "loopy." This data set was then randomly divided into 1400 training lines and 400 validation lines, taking care to ensure that the fraction of "loopy" lines was the same in each set. The network was then trained on these lines using Stochastic Gradient Descent (Zinkevich et al., 2010) with a Cross-Entropy loss function, defined by

$$J_{CE}(x, y) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^2 w_i (-y_i + \log \sum_{j=1}^2 e^{x_j})}{\sum_{i=1}^2 w_i}, \quad (7)$$

for an output vector x with expected return y and class weights w . Networks were trained for 1000 epochs with a learning rate of 5×10^{-5} and a momentum of 0.35. A dropout factor of 0.2 was used in the convolution layers and 0.5 in the linear layers to prevent overdependence on any single node. After training many such networks, measures of their performance were used to identify the best version of the network. The highest performing network had probability of detection $POD = C_L/N_L = 0.96$, where C_L is the number of correctly identified loop lines, and N_L the total number of loop lines, a false positive rate $FPR = I_L/(C_L + I_L) = 0.04$, with I_L the number of non-loop lines judged to be loopy, and a true skill statistic $TSS = C_L/N_L - I_L/N_N = 0.94$, with

Figure 4: Schematic representation of the W-net segmentation network. Yellow boxes represent convolution layers, while orange boxes are linear rectification. Red boxes are pooling layers, and blue boxes are transposed convolutions. The purple box labelled *SOFT* is a derivative-preserving softmax layer. Multiple arrows meeting indicates a concatenation of data products.

N_N the total number of non-loopy field lines.

The segmentation network is adapted from an architecture that has come to be called a W-net (e.g. Xia & Kulis 2017), a schematic of which is shown in Figure 4. W-nets are combination encoder-decoders, popular for their ability to train unsupervised, which is to say without the guidance of pre-determined "correct" answers, on image segmentation tasks. In testing, we found that our W-nets were most successful when operating on a reprocessed subset of the physical quantities available, namely dr_{cyl}/ds , $d|z|/ds$, κ , $|B_r|$, β , and S' . We trained our segmentation networks on the 14086 field lines from our total set of 91000 which had loop scores of at least 0.5, again with Stochastic Gradient Descent, for 1400 epochs using a learning rate of 2.5×10^{-4} , momentum of 0.25, and a dropout of 0.2 in all convolution layers. Losses were calculated twice per epoch, applying Soft-N-Cut Loss to the output of the encoder, intercepted after the softmax layer, and an RMS error loss to the output of the decoder, which is expected to reproduce the input image. The Soft-N-Cut loss is defined as

$$J_{SNC,K}(u) = K - \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N u_{i,k} \sum_{j=1}^N w_{i,j} u_{j,k}}{\sum_{i=1}^N u_{i,k} \sum_{j=1}^N w_{i,j}}, \quad (8)$$

where u is the tensor output of the encoder section of the network, with probabilities of belonging to each of K classes for each of the N points along the field line. The weights invoked are defined as

$$w_{i,j} = e^{-(i-j)^2/\sigma_x^2 - \|F_i - F_j\|^2/\sigma_F^2}, \quad (9)$$

if $|i - j| < r_x$ and 0 otherwise, where F_i is the vector of normalized physical quantities for the i th point along the field line. Our segmentation networks were trained with $K = 4$, $\sigma_x = 4$, $\sigma_F = 10$, and $r_x = 5$.

The decoder component of the W-net exists solely to keep it grounded while training. In practice, the pointwise classification produced by the encoder is the only output of interest. Due to the inhomogeneity of rising loops, no models were found in which loop candidates could be consistently identified from a single classification. Instead, our loop candidates are identified by searching the segmented line for certain se-

quences of classes (e.g. rising arm, loop crest, descending arm), which has proven to be quite robust.

5 Conclusions

Although self-consistent rising magnetic loops are generally few and far between in all but the most turbulent convective dynamo simulations, a catastrophic release of magnetic energy from its reservoir in the tachocline of a simulated M2 star has yielded an abundance of these rare structures for our analysis. A series of tracings of an example rising loop found in this model is presented in Figure 5. Using a hand-identified subset of these loops as a training set, we have developed a machine-learning-enabled pipeline for the identification and tracking of rising magnetic flux ropes in global spherical convective dynamo simulations.

The neural network solutions for the identification of loop candidates based on thousands of integrated field lines show both high accuracy in their assessments and high completeness in their overall surveys of the computational domain. The routines enabling the tracking of loop candidates identified across timesteps, however, still face unresolved challenges. Firstly, imprecise predictions for the evolution of a magnetic field line in a resistive regime require that a broad net be cast when looking for the successor to that field line in the following time step, which tends to lead to high multiplicity in matches. While it is entirely possible that one loop candidate may split into multiple, or that multiple may merge together, we find that in its current state, our tracking algorithm dramatically overestimates the incidence rate for these phenomena. Secondly, in cases where two or more loop candidates are identified along the same field line, the segmentation network can at times struggle to keep them distinct. If two candidates are identified at one time, but considered part of the same loop at a later time, and later still regain their individuality, spuriously fast rises can be inferred from the resulting match multiplicity.

Despite these challenges, we are optimistic that the pipeline we have developed will soon enable complete, systematic searches for rising magnetic loops in dynamo simulations, regardless of whether that rise is driven by buoyant superequipartition magnetic fields, simple advection, or a combination thereof. We have already verified that the neu-

Figure 5: Field line tracings through a rising loop done without the aid of the pipeline presented here, seen from above the north pole at 3 instants each separated by roughly 24 days. Color encodes magnetic field amplitude, with yellows in excess of 30 kG and black for fields of <2 kG.

ral networks perform well in models of FC M4 ($0.3M_{\odot}$) stars, without any need for retraining, and are thus hopeful that the same will hold true for shallower, solar-like CZs as well. Once the remaining issues with the tracking routine have been resolved, the pipeline will be made freely available to facilitate a better understanding of the processes leading to flux emergence in a wide variety of stars.

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